

Protocol Literature Review: Data Debt: Concept, Taxonomy, Best Practices and Research Agenda

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Introduction

This review protocol has been developed in accordance with the PRISMA guidelines as shown the Fig. 1.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram for literature review.

Review Rationale

The concept of data debt is emerging across information systems, data governance, and machine learning literature. The terminology is heterogeneous and scattered across academic and professional sources. A scoping review is appropriate to:

- Map definitions and conceptualizations.
- Identify taxonomies and dimensions.
- Examine management and governance approaches.
- Detect theoretical and empirical gaps

Review Questions

RQ1 How is data debt conceptualized in academic and professional literature?

RQ2 What dimensions or taxonomies of data debt are proposed?

RQ3 What management, governance, or remediation approaches are suggested?

RQ4 What research gaps remain in the study of data debt?

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- Use of terms: "data debt", "data technical debt", "information debt".
- Discussion of debt related to data management, governance, analytics, or AI.
- Academic articles, book chapters, conference papers, or substantial professional sources.
- English or Spanish.

Exclusion criteria:

- Duplicate.
- Purely financial debt without data relation.
- Publication year (2016 or before)
- Without substantive reference to data or information

Information Sources

- Scopus
- IEEE Xplore
- Targeted grey literature (vendor blogs, consulting reports, professional essays)

Date of last search: December 2025.

Search Strategy

Scopus:

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("data debt" OR "data technical debt" OR "information debt") OR ("data management debt" OR "analytics debt" OR "information quality debt") OR ("technical debt" AND ("data" OR "information")) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("decision making" OR "organizational performance" OR "digital transformation" OR "data analytics")

IEEE Xplore:

("data debt" OR "data technical debt" OR "information debt") OR ("Data management debt" OR "Analytics debt" OR "Information quality debt")

Selection Process

Export of records

Title	Author (s)	Year	Source
A Generalized Approach to Data Supply Chain Management – Balancing Data Value and Data Debt	Maranca, R.; Staiano, M.	2021	Web
A Review on Hidden Debts in Machine Learning Systems	Chaudhary, D. K.; Srivastava, S.; Kumar, V.	2018	IEEE Xplore
Accounting conservatism, debt covenants, and information asymmetry	Din, N. U.; Cheng, X.; Nazneen, S.	2017	IEEE Xplore
Aligning Data Debt with AI-Integrated Software Project Lifecycle Processes: A Standard-Based Mapping Approach	Akgül, N.Y.; Taşkaya-Temizel, T.T.; Özcan-Top, Ö.Ö.; Akman, P.D.	2025	IEEE Xplore
Aligning Data Debt with AI-Integrated Software Project Lifecycle Processes: A Standard-Based Mapping Approach	Akgül, N.Y.; Taşkaya-Temizel, T.T.; Özcan-Top, Ö.Ö.; Akman, P.D.	2025	Scopus
Asymmetric Information, Debt Capacity, and Capital Structure	Lemmon, M.L.; Zender, J.F.	2019	Scopus
Automated Identification of Machine Learning Technical Debt Code Comments	Khanvilkar, O.; Mkaouer, M.W.; Abdullah Alomar, E.A.; Elsaid, A.; Chaaben, A.; Touati, M.	2025	IEEE Xplore
Automated Identification of Machine Learning Technical Debt Code Comments	Khanvilkar, O.; Mkaouer, M.W.; Abdullah Alomar, E.A.; Elsaid, A.; Chaaben, A.; Touati, M.	2025	Scopus
Computer Intelligent Evaluation Model and Research on the Mathematical Impact of Hiring Decisions Using Big Data Technology	Zhang, C.; Liu, Z.; Zhang, Y.; Lv, L.	2021	IEEE Xplore

Title	Author (s)	Year	Source
Data Analytics on Debt Financing Research Based on Scopus and WoS Metrics	Veres, O.; Ilchuk, P.; Kots, O.	2023	IEEE Xplore
Data Debt – What Is It and How Does It Impact Organizations?	Cole, Z.	2022	Web
Data Debt: Addressing Enterprise Data Quality Problems	Ambler, S.	n.d.	Web
Data Debt: The Silent Killer of Data-Driven Organizations	Rasikuhail	2023	Web
Data Debt: What Is it and How to Avoid It	Freeman, M.	2023	Web
Data Debt: what it is and how to estimate it	Travkin, P.	2020	Web
Data Smells Are Sneaky	Hahn, N.; Sales, A.	2025	Scopus
Determinants of the Value Relevance of Accounting Information in Emerging Economies: Evidence from Iraq	Al-Jawaheri, B.A.W.; Najm, K.; Hussein MacHi, A.	2021	Scopus
Does the industrial big data environment matter? An evaluation of its effect on the production performance	Hou, L.	2025	Scopus
Double Empirical Bayes Testing	Tansey, W.; Wang, Y.; Rabadán, R.; Blei, D.	2020	Scopus
Energy Poverty Clustering by Using Power-cut Job Order Data of the Electricity Distribution Companies	Emre, T.; Sözen, A.	2022	Scopus
Environmental Information Provisions and Response of the Market: Empirical Analysis of PRTRs in Japan	Hibiki, A.; Managi, S.	2006	IEEE Xplore
Error Rate Analysis for Random Linear Streaming Codes in the Finite Memory Length Regime	Su, P.-W.; Huang, Y.-C.; Lin, S.-C.; Wang, I.-H.; Wang, C.-C.	2020	IEEE Xplore
Error Rate Analysis for Random Linear Streaming Codes in the Finite Memory Length Regime	Su, P.-W.; Huang, Y.-C.; Lin, S.-C.; Wang, I.-H.; Wang, C.-C.	2020	Scopus
Evidence for communicative compensation in debt advice with reduced multimodality	Andelic, N.; Feeney, A.; McKeown, G.	2019	Scopus
Explicit Information-Debt-Optimal Streaming Codes With Small Memory	Krishnan, M.N.; Vajha, M.; Ramkumar, V.; Vijay Kumar, P.V.	2023	IEEE Xplore
Explicit Information-Debt-Optimal Streaming Codes With Small Memory	Krishnan, M.N.; Vajha, M.; Ramkumar, V.; Vijay Kumar, P.V.	2023	Scopus
Implementing AI in Mexico’s Health Sector: A Strategic Framework	Lerma-Torres, D.C.	2025	Scopus

Title	Author (s)	Year	Source
Incomplete Information, Debt Issuance, and the Term Structure of Credit Spreads	Benzoni, L.; Garlappi, L.; Goldstein, R.	2023	Scopus
Modelling debt financing behaviour of Malaysia SMEs	Haron, R.	2015	IEEE Xplore
Non-linearity in the determinants of capital structure: Evidence from Selected Indian pharmaceutical companies	Sinha S.; Samanta, P. K.	2014	IEEE Xplore
Notice of Retraction: Debt contract, accounting information and the creditors' supervision	Jiang, L.	2011	IEEE Xplore
On Information-Debt-Optimal Streaming Codes With Small Memory	Ramkumar, V.; Krishnan, M.N.; Vajha, M.; Vijay Kumar, P.V.	2022	IEEE Xplore
On Information-Debt-Optimal Streaming Codes With Small Memory	Ramkumar, V.; Krishnan, M.N.; Vajha, M.; Vijay Kumar, P.V.	2022	Scopus
Privacy, privation, and person: Data, debt, and infrastructured personhood	Park, E.; Donovan, K.P.	2023	Scopus
Study on enterprise comprehensive performance assessment mechanism	Li, J.	2012	IEEE Xplore
The data debt hindering your digital transformation	Visch, J.; Benson, J.	2022	Web
The effects of a focal firm's internal and external boundary conditions on the performance implication of R&D alliance participation	Cheng-Yu, L.; Ming-Chao, W.; Jung-Ching, L.	2011	IEEE Xplore
The Evaluation on Financial Risks of Listed Companies - Based on the Empirical Evidence from Chinese Stock Market	Zhu, N.; Zhu, L.	2011	IEEE Xplore
The Five Nine: Telcos are drowning in data	Goovaerts, D.	2025	Web
The four big forces conspiring to ruin one's analytics	Greenhouse, J.	2021	Scopus
The four main categories of Data Debt explained	Matillion	2024	Web
The impact of financial leverage to profitability study of non-financial companies listed in Indonesia stock exchange	Singapurwoko, A.; el-Wahid, M.S.M.	2011	Scopus
What Is Data Debt & How Do You Avoid It?	Mizrahi, E.	2024	Web

Removal of duplicates

Title	Author (s)	Year
Aligning Data Debt with AI-Integrated Software Project Lifecycle Processes: A Standard-Based Mapping Approach	Akgül, N.Y.; Taşkaya-Temizel, T.T.; Özcan-Top, Ö.Ö.; Akman, P.D.	2025
Automated Identification of Machine Learning Technical Debt Code Comments	Khanvilkar, O.; Mkaouer, M.W.; Abdullah Alomar, E.A.; Elsaid, A.; Chaaben, A.; Touati, M.	2025
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Accounting conservatism, debt covenants, and information asymmetry	Din, N. U.; Cheng, X.; Nazneen, S.	2017
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Full-text eligibility assessment data base (IEEE Xplore and Scopus)

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The four big forces conspiring to ruin one's analytics	Greenhouse, J.	2021	Scopus

Screening conducted by two reviewers; discrepancies resolved by discussion.

Data Charting Process

A structured extraction matrix was developed including:

- Definition of “data debt”
- Main dimensions/types
- Predominant domain of application
- Implications for decisions and performance
- Explicit relationship with digital transformation

Data Items

Variables extracted:

- Conceptual definition
- Taxonomy categories

Critical Appraisal

Consistent with scoping review methodology, no formal methodological quality assessment was conducted. The objective was mapping, not evaluation of effect sizes.

Results

Selected final document (include database and other sources):

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What Is Data Debt & How Do You Avoid It?	Mizrahi, E.	2024	Web

Results of individual sources of evidence

A general reading of the documents was carried out to identify relevant aspects for analysis. Then, using ChatGPT 3.5 and attaching the documents, iterations were made based on the following prompt to organize the information:

“For each attached document, extract structured information related to: Whether it is related to data debt, type of contribution (theoretical, empirical, technical), domain of application (software, data governance, analytics/AI, others), how the concept of debt is defined or used: associated dimensions or categories, methods used, and main implications for decision-making, organizational performance, or digital transformation.”

For example:

Document	Author (s)	Definition and relationship to “data debt”	Main dimensions or types of data debt	Predominant domain of application	Type of contribution, methods and implications	Explicit relationship with digital transformation
A Generalized Approach to Data Supply Chain Management – Balancing Data Value and Data Debt	Maranca, R.; Staiano, M.	Directly addresses data debt as a central variable in the data supply chain (DSC) model. It is not generic technical debt, but rather an economic measure linked to data quality and the value that can be extracted from it.	Defines a minimum data supply chain (source S, extraction processes P_e, quality processes P_q, visualization P_v, consumer A, value V). For each data set D_i and quality rule Q_ij with tolerance L_ij, the necessary uplift is quantified as M_ij = $\mu(Q_{ij} - L_{ij})$. The company's data debt is the sum ΣM_{ij} : the theoretical cost necessary to raise quality to the threshold demanded by data consumers and capture the expected value.	Business data management and data supply chains in highly digitized organizations ("modern digital enterprises"), linking data quality, chain complexity, and value creation.	Mainly theoretical/analytical contribution, with a formal DSC model and a debt quantification scheme + simple numerical example. There is no empirical study with companies, but there is an illustrative application using a CRM case study.	Data debt is interpreted as a "cost hurdle" that the chain must overcome in order to contribute positively to the bottom line; it can be integrated into activity-based costing models to make the cost of poor data quality explicit in investment decisions. The model explicitly links the reduction of data debt t, the POC/MVP phases of data projects, and the ability of companies to face the "digital challenges of the future"; in other words, it is a critical input for data-driven digital transformation.
Data Debt: What Is it and How to Avoid It	Freeman, M.	Data debt = shortcuts and compromises in data quality, data architecture, and data management to speed up access to data; it accumulates over time and creates significant long-term challenges. It is clearly distinct from technical debt, which is more focused on hardware/software.	There is no formal typology, but it proposes: 13 symptoms (integration problems, project delays, system degradation, bad decisions, missed opportunities, low productivity, increased costs, security vulnerabilities, regulatory issues, low morale, dissatisfied customers, reputational damage, loss of competitive advantage); and best practices grouped into three categories: procedural, technological, cultural ("people, processes, technologies").	Data-driven organizations and modern data stack (data quality, integration, data contracts, data platforms).	Debt compromises decision-making, creates inefficiencies, increases operating costs, raises security risks and regulatory penalties, damages morale and customer experience, and can harm reputation.	It explicitly links debt management to the classic triad of digital transformation (people, processes, technologies), and warns that organizations "drowning in data debt" lose their ability to innovate and ultimately lose their competitive advantage.

For more details, see the supplementary file: *Review_DataDebt.xlsx*

Conceptual contribution of sources to taxonomy

The expanded results are described in the paper through the questions posed for this purpose. Sections are developed as described below:

3.1. Conceptualizing data debt. This section is developed with a proposal for conceptualizing data debt. Emphasis is placed on comparing and establishing the differences between data debt, technical debt, and financial debt.

3.2. Proposal taxonomy.

3.3. Data debt management: best practices. Some best practices associated with debt management grouped into four items: discovery, assessment and prioritization, repayment execution and ongoing governance. For each item we describe: problems, conflicting forces, best practices and results.

3.4. Research agenda. Emphasis is placed on comparing and establishing the differences between data debt, technical debt, and financial debt. We present three major lines of research that contribute to the development of this field, providing descriptions and questions for those interested in this area.

The conceptual contribution of the sources to the taxonomy is systematized using the following matrix that cross-references the eight identified types of data debt with the selected sources.

Type of data debt	Conceptual descriptors	Main roles involved	References
<i>Data quality debt</i>	Reliability of information; fitness for use; integrity and consistency of records; stability of metrics; effective informational value.	Data owners, data stewards, business process managers, data quality manager, BI/Analytics team.	Cole, Z. (2022); Ambler, S. (n.d.); Matillion (2024); Rasiksuhail (2023); Travkin, P. (2020); Visch, J.; Benson, J. (2022).
<i>Metadata and lineage debt</i>	Semantic transparency; traceability of origin and use; interpretability of data; visibility of information flow; discoverability of data assets.	CDO, metadata manager, data stewards, data architects, internal/external auditors.	Freeman, M. (2023); Mizrahi, E. (2024).
<i>Data model debt</i>	Conceptual representation of the business; semantic consistency between systems; structural stability of data; normalization of master entities; business-data alignment.	Data architects, data modelers, domain data owners, solutions architect, MDM team.	Maranca, R.; Staiano, M. (2021); Matillion (2024).
<i>Integration and interoperability debt</i>	Data flow continuity; coupling between systems; reuse of data services; interface standardization; cohesion of the information ecosystem.	Data engineers, integration architects, enterprise architect, CIO/CTO, platform and API managers.	Maranca, R.; Staiano, M. (2021); Cole, Z. (2022); Travkin, P. (2020).
<i>Analytics, modeling, and AI debt</i>	Analytical robustness; reproducibility of results; model explainability; analytical lifecycle governance; fairness and absence of bias.	Head of Analytics/AI, data scientists, ML engineers, data engineers, MLOps team, analytical product owners.	Chaudhary, D. K.; Srivastava, S.; Kumar, V. (2018); Akgül, N.Y.; Taşkaya-Temizel, T.T.; Özcan-Top, Ö.Ö.; Akman, P.D. (2025); Greenhouse, J. (2021); Hahn, N.; Sales, A. (2025); Khanvilkar, O.; Mkaouer, M.W.; Abdullah Alomar, E.A.; Elsaid, A.; Chaaben, A.; Touati, M. (2025); Lerma-Torres, D.C. (2025).
<i>Compliance, ethics, and security debt</i>	Personal data protection; legitimacy of processing; confidentiality and access control; algorithmic responsibility; regulatory compliance.	DPO, CISO, legal and compliance area, CDO, security architects, business managers in regulated domains.	Visch, J.; Benson, J. (2022); Greenhouse, J. (2021); Matillion (2024); Travkin, P. (2020).
<i>Data documentation debt</i>	Outsourcing of knowledge; formalization of data rules; persistence of expert knowledge; accessibility of technical knowledge; maintainability of artifacts.	Data stewards, technical leaders, data engineers, data scientists, data architects, PMO/project office.	Rasiksuhail (2023); Freeman, M. (2023); Mizrahi, E. (2024); Mizrahi, E. (2024); Travkin, P. (2020).
<i>Data infrastructure debt</i>	Platform capacity and scalability; operational resilience; observability of the data environment; architectural flexibility; technology-strategy alignment.	CIO/CTO, infrastructure architect, data platform owner, SRE/DevOps, data engineers, corporate IT managers.	Maranca, R.; Staiano, M. (2021); Goovaerts, D. (2025); Greenhouse, J. (2021); Hou, L. (2025); Matillion (2024); Visch, J.; Benson, J. (2022).